

A publishers' anatomy through Argentina's scholarly output: exploring evaluation path dependency

Fernanda Beigel – CONICET-UNCuyo, FCPyS, Ciudad de Mendoza, Provincia de Mendoza, Argentina – fernandabeigel@gmail.com – ORCID: 0000-0002-7996-9660

Duban Torres Arroyave - Vicerrectoría de Investigación, Universidad del Rosario, Bogotá, Colombia.

CoLaV, Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín, Colombia.

Gabriel Vélez Cuartas - Departamento de Sociología, CoLaV, Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín, Colombia.

Abstract

This paper presents an in-depth analysis of scholarly publishing through the lens of Argentina's scientific output focusing on the diversity of the publishers and the incidence of the global standards of academic evaluation in this landscape. We explore what we call "evaluation path dependency" between 2013 and 2020, considering that it is after 2020 when paid Open Access was effectively accelerated in Europe and this radiography explains the main effects in an internationalized academic elite subject to financial constraints. Drawing on a multisource database of over 139,000 articles, the study classifies publishers according to their institutional anchorage or commercial nature, observing different publishing circuits, access routes, and capturing the Article Processing Charges (APCs) in this pre-acceleration phase. The findings reveal a concentration of journals edited by commercial publishers, whose dominance is reinforced through alliances with professional societies and the adoption of hybrid and gold open-access models. These alliances increase publication costs and often hinder open access in semi-peripheral countries like Argentina. At the same time, university journals and diamond open access plays a significant role, though struggling with limited visibility. By mapping publisher alliances and evaluating the degree of dependency across disciplines, the paper identifies two main models of knowledge circulation: monetized and non-monetized. The research shows that the national evaluation system incentivizes publication in high-impact journals, reinforcing commercial circuits and hybrid models, while marginalizing local and nonprofit open access editorial efforts. Nonetheless, the persistence of diverse publishing alliances and the resilience of university-led initiatives highlight ongoing opportunities for alternative, inclusive, and sustainable scholarly communication. The study calls for greater recognition of diamond university journals and regional publishing platforms as key elements in fostering equitable knowledge dissemination and reducing structural inequalities in global academic publishing.

Keywords

Open Access - Scholarly Publishing - Article Processing Charges (APC) - Publishers - Research Evaluation

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As noted by several studies around the 20-year balance from the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI, 2002), open access emerged with a noble intention but has evolved into a flawed reality (Tennant et al., 2019; Frank, Foster & Pagliari, 2023). Vested interests within the academic publishing sector, particularly among publishers of highly esteemed journals (e.g. those with Impact Factors above 10–20), have been strongly motivated to adopt hybrid funding models (De Castro et al 2024). These publishers continue to receive substantial subscription revenue despite high prices, while also experiencing a steady influx of manuscript submissions that far exceed their publication capacity. They not only obtain profit through the payment of Article Processing Charges (APC) but, increasingly, through *Read & Publish* agreements¹. A dynamic drift of scholarly journals demanding increasingly high APC overshadowed the achievements of the open access movement and significantly impacted the publishing market (Morrison et al., 2022).

Over the past fifteen years, the ecosystem of scientific journals has become highly diversified: large public universities that publish diamond journals co-exist with commercial university presses that publish journals with high APCs: numerous journals previously published by learned societies have been acquired by large publishing groups (Delgado-López-Cozar & Martín-Martín, 2024). A growing concentration of high-impact journals within an oligopoly of commercial publishers has been observed (Larivière, Haustein, Mongeon, 2015; Haustein, Mongeon, 2023). This aligns with the findings by Butler et al. (2023), who reported that the growth in the volume of open access articles among the 'big five'² publishers between 2015 and 2018 resulted in approximately 1.06 billion USD in additional revenue. Alongside these publishers, journals managed by major professional associations and large university presses—primarily based in the United States and the United Kingdom—also play a significant role in scholarly publishing. These entities actively participate in the scholarly publishing market and compete for bibliometric impact and journal ranking positions. Meanwhile, the mega-journals created in open access and operated under the gold business model penetrated the audience of the most diverse research fields, reaching high-impact indicators, thus redefining the relationship between the journals and the research communities (Ellers et al., 2017).

The prestige gained by these journals has enabled them to raise subscription fees and generate additional revenue by increasing APCs. Through initiatives such as Coalition S and the European Union's open access policies, this shift in the business model was largely funded by universities and governments—an approach that ultimately served to reinforce the dominance of publishing oligopolies (Anderson, 2023). In fact, Coalition S itself now reports that over two thirds of the 'transformative journals' permitted to receive funding from organizations participating in the Plan S open access initiative are to be excluded from the scheme for failing to meet their targets³.

¹ These agreements have advanced decidedly in Europe but to a lesser extent in Latin America where several countries have national subscriptions with publishers. Due to budgetary restrictions, it is not likely that universities will be able to sign these agreements either. See Godínez Larios (2024).

² Elsevier, Springer-Nature, Sage, Wolters Kluwer (Taylor & Francis owners), MDPI. Nonetheless, the commercial model is present in other editorial houses as Frontiers, IEEE, and others.

³ <https://www.researchprofessionalnews.com/rr-news-europe-infrastructure-2023-6-68-of-transformative-journals-to-be-kicked-out-of-plan-s-scheme/>

With the rise of open access and large-scale scientific infrastructures, some scholars have suggested that traditional journals may eventually disappear, replaced by platform-based publishing models (Guédon, 2021; Mercado, Vessuri et al., 2023). However, journals continue to proliferate due to the recognition they confer and the role they play in research evaluation systems as guarantors of the quality of published results.

Citation indexes stratify recognition and serve as the final link in the consecration of journals, even as the boundaries between such indexes and the traditional concept of the scientific journal become increasingly blurred. These impact indices and journal rankings not only amplify the prestige of the journals themselves but also that of the publication platforms—such as WoS and Scopus—which have become highly profitable enterprises by selling journal package subscriptions to universities and national institutions (Delgado-López-Cózar & Martín-Martín, 2024). Paid open access is generating two major effects: the stratification of open access publishing (Klebel & Ross-Hellauer, 2023) and the monetization of prestige, whereby APC pricing is supposedly calculated according to impact factors (Halevi et al., 2024). There is evidence that this is starting to prompt a potential retreat from the open access movement, as researchers from low-income countries are increasingly unable to afford publication fees. For example, the backwardness observed particularly in the increasing choice of closed publishing in hybrid journals in the output of Argentina's largest scientific agency, the CONICET (Vélez Cuartas, Beigel et al. 2022). "My articles are not available in open access, but they are published in the good journals that we all read, and we don't have to face paywalls" says a senior researcher in medicine that participated in a focus group (Beigel & Gallardo, 2022).

Although some argue that the specter of predatory publishing has begun to fade (Richtig et al., 2023), questionable journals continue to haunt the academia, even within the most reputable publishing houses, undermining the scientific credibility of journals that once relied on trust in the excellence of the editorial process. Commercial Open Access has played a significant role in this shift, although the gold open access model proposed in the Budapest Open Access Declaration (2002) initially referred to cost-free access. Later, the Open Access Movement introduced the term "Diamond Open Access" to distinguish free open access models from those requiring APC payments.

The commodification of scholarly publishing can lead to a significant accumulation of recognition driven by non-academic factors, establishing a dependency path. In this way, the dominant value regime that structures publishing practices is built upon global evaluation criteria applied through institutional research assessment. A continuous accumulation of publishing decisions dependent on "high-impact" evaluation-system rewards, thus, limit the options for the development of career-building within the constraints of a given field.

The concept of path dependency explains the outcome of a technological process that depends on a cumulative sequence of past decisions rather than the current situation alone. It emphasizes the importance of choices in shaping subsequent actions. Schienstock (2007) argues that path dependency is characteristic of institutional development, and there is evidence that differences across countries play a crucial role in shaping and channeling technological change. For our purposes, this means that research communities may have different degrees of path dependency from the main publishing commercial houses, featured by the national or institutional conditions to which the researchers' careers are subject. To explore this, it is critical to go beyond the limitations of Web of Science (Clarivate) as bibliometric data source because the dominant role played by the Impact Factor in this publishing circuit tends to exacerbate this path dependency pattern. Indeed, several studies have analyzed the production of Latin American countries

arriving to the conclusion that more than half of these articles were published in journals edited by oligopoly publishers (Neubert & Rodrigues, 2021). In the case of Brazil, when the source is solely WoS this share arises to 74,74% (Anselmo, Rodrigues & Mugnaini, 2023). In contrast, broader datasources show the existence of a wider margin for maneuvering in career-building that has allowed multiscale styles of scholarly publishing. As argued by Kulczycki et al. (2025) observed from the output of a non-hegemonic research community, the publishers emerge as a highly diverse phenomenon, while new alliances between academic and commercial publishers can be observed.

Momeni et al. (2023) employed correlation and regression analysis to examine how income levels, impact, and circulation routes influence publishing behavior. Their results underscored the structural limitations of the open access advantage for low-income countries based on author affiliation, their route choice, and the citation impact of their work. Similarly, Nichols & Twidale (2017) have developed metrics to observe the public availability of open materials, or the monopoly of open access strategies, as also seen in of Butler et al. (2023). However, none of these studies have observed the behavior of researchers concerning the circulation possibilities offered by the different publication models, according to the expectations of their disciplinary fields. To explore these different available circuits, we examine the various alliances between publishers that offer similar conditions for disseminating knowledge in different domains. Through this, we observe the effects in a path dependent strategy for the circulation of knowledge that costs increasingly more money for the researchers. In contrast, a senior or established author who publishes by invitation in hybrid journals can be less dependent on the constraints imposed by commercial publishing, although his/her research will not be available in open access. Even more autonomous seems the researcher who publishes in diamond open access journals, but the visibility of these university publishers can be limited.

In this paper, we analyze the transformation of the publishing industry from the perspective of a scientific field that is structurally heterogeneous, combining nationally oriented researchers with internationally integrated elites, crossed-through by several publishing circuits (Beigel, 2014). Focusing on the scientific output of Argentina allows us to observe a research community that plays a dominated role in the global circulation of knowledge, but a central place among other countries in the Latin American region. This provides an anatomy of a more complete array of publishers and their interactions, deconstructing the agents behind scholarly journals, capturing commercial publishers and academic publishing institutions whereas there is one in charge, typically referred as the “corporate author” in the Ulrich database⁴. Observing the strategies of the commercial publishers employed until 2020 highlights how they managed to dominate, or even co-opt, journals formerly published by learned societies that are now owned by the “big 5” publishers or their diverse branches.

Finally, we examine the different routes of access used by CONICET researchers observing new tendencies emerging in a non-hegemonic country adapting to the new restrictions imposed by paid open access. Special attention is given to hybrid journals that have been scarcely studied while more researchers opt for publishing in this old-style subscription model to face financial restrictions. Finally, we observe the different networks of publisher’s alliances apparently in the

⁴ The concept of “corporate author” used by Ulrich is used in this paper only as an initial information to elucidate the owner of the journals., checked afterwards through our multi-source database. For a discussion of the classification of the publishers based on the distinction between commercial publishing and academic editorship See Beigel, F. (2025). The transformative relation between publishers and editors: research quality and academic autonomy at stake. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 6, 154–170. <https://doi.org/10.1162/qss.a.00343>

move to find new forms to valorize scholarly journals. A dynamic that could ultimately undermine academic autonomy and the advancement of equitable and inclusive open science.

1.1. The becoming of Gold Open Access and the transformation of scholarly publishing

In its early stages, the private scientific publishing industry operated under a closed model, restricting access through subscriptions and direct sales in order to secure stable revenue streams and control the distribution of knowledge (Guerra González, 2017). This approach had already sparked debate as early as the 1980s, due to the high subscription costs. Initially, librarians raised concerns over these costs, arguing that knowledge, as a “public good,” should always be available to everyone (Byrd, 1990). With the advent of electronic journals, this debate was reignited, as digital formats significantly reduced publishing costs. It was therefore argued that competitive advantages would increasingly depend on the underlying philosophy of the publishing model (Schauder, 1994).

The development of ICTs in recent decades enabled the diversification of knowledge dissemination channels. Several open access models emerged to broaden or guarantee access to scholarly content most notably the green, hybrid, and gold routes. The green model refers to self-archiving in institutional repositories; the hybrid model allows authors to choose whether their article is open access; and the gold model requires an author payment to make the article freely accessible. However, these models also sparked debate regarding the financial sustainability of open access (Melero & Abad García, 2011; Bird, 2008). They represent varying degrees of openness, with the gold model offering the broadest access by providing full access to the article, but also imposing financial barriers to publication (Solomon & Björk, 2012), which in turn impact citation rates and visibility (Langham-Putrow et al., 2021). Despite this openness, the gold model remains distant from the philosophical principle of knowledge as a “public good,” which advocates that knowledge should be accessible to all without financial barriers.

To fully embody this ideal alternative open access pathways have emerged that remove all barriers: the black model, characterized by unauthorized access to academic content, also referred to as piracy (Björk, 2017), and the diamond model, in which neither readers nor authors pay fees, with editorial funding sourced from public investments and academic institutions (Fuchs & Sandoval, 2013).

From the perspective of peripheral countries, the APC-based open access model exacerbates inequalities in access to scientific knowledge (Córdoba González, 2020; Debat & Babini, 2020). Moreover, the distinction between academic and so-called “predatory” journals is increasingly difficult to establish given the growing commercialization of scholarly communication. Predatory journals are typically lack rigor that can operate as businesses or even scams. Indeed, the rise of open access journals that promise rapid publication and leverage the ease of online platforms has led to a class of journals that forego peer review and whose sole objective is to collect APCs from individuals seeking to rapidly “inflate” their publication record. However, the boundary between predatory and non-predatory journals is becoming blurred, along with the distinction between academic journals and those completely managed by a commercial publisher. Ultimately, what is at stake is the academic context of the journals—those co-opted by commercial interests may not be strictly predatory but certainly fall into the category of “questionable” (Pölönen & Sivertsen, 2021).

The evolving relationship between academic journals and the publishing industry remains insufficiently explored, which is directly linked to the emergence of commercial citation indexes and platforms such as Elsevier’s ScienceDirect (1997), SpringerLink (1996), Wiley InterScience–Online Library (1997), SAGE Journals (2004), and Taylor & Francis Online (2011) (Bakkalbasi et al., 2006; Fyfe et al., 2022; Taşkın, Pölönen, Kulczycki & Laakso, 2023). These publishing houses played a pivotal role in the early days of the internet by providing intermediary services between journals and readers. Over time, however, they began to offer comprehensive editorial management services, including peer review, layout and design, and distribution through online platforms.

According to the available literature, the direct involvement of publishing oligopolies in editorial management fundamentally altered scholarly publishing (Larivière, Haustein, Mongeon, 2015; Haustein, Mongeon, 2023). As commercial publishers assumed control of editorial workflows, they also began curating content and academic processes to align with scientometric indicators and enhance journal rankings in international databases. This evolution unfolded differently for independent journals, those run by learned societies, and university-affiliated journals. On the one hand, journals affiliated with professional associations or universities often outsource academic functions as the volume and demand for articles increase. On the other hand, universities and governments subscribing to the agreements proposed by publishers are subject to terms imposed by commercial firms, with limited or no bargaining power. From the perspective of end-users (i.e., researchers), this results in restricted rather than democratized access—both reading and publishing are limited to individuals whose institutions can afford the costs.

2. Data & methods

Due to the ongoing transformations referred above, the classification of the publishers in the traditional databases is becoming increasingly unstable, because the institutional anchoring of journals is rapidly shifting from scientific societies or universities to commercial publishers. Gu & Blackmore (2017) built a dataset with the relevant attributes identified in Ulrichs, JCR, SJR, GS, and Cabells, showing that some key attributes are not well captured in the existing bibliographic sources. Furthermore, the lack of a formal data dictionary leads to inconsistencies across data collection agencies and organizations. It has become increasingly relevant to distinguish which organization, company or institution is truly in charge of the editorial processes and academic decisions in a journal. In the category of “educational institutions” very often we see included commercial university presses, research institutes and independent journals published by a research team.

A growing body of literature addresses the classification of the publishers, from which at least seven categories of publishers can be distinguished: (a) Large for-profit publisher, (b) Not-for-profit organization, (c) University press, (d) Professional association, (e) Small for-profit publisher, (f) University or educational institutions, (g) Government, and g) a final group of uncategorized (Siler & Frenken, 2020; Siler & Larivière, 2022; Taşkın, Pölönen, Kulczycki and Laakso 2023). To address the combinations between commercial publishers, learned societies and universities, as well as the distinctive non-commercial journals, we deconstructed Ulrich’s two-folded information provided on the publishers. It separates the “commercial publisher” and the “corporate author”, the latter being “the owner” of the journal. The advantage of this information is that we can explore a typology built to distinguish academic and commercial actors. Considering the objectives of this study the following classification of publishers according to their institutional nature is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Classification of publishers.

Category	n
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Professional societies/Learned societies	1762
University	1533
Others	674
Foundation / Mega-journal	287
Commercial publisher	248
Centre/Centro	110
University press/Editorial Universitaria	109
Governmental	64
Colegio/College/Escuela	56
Journal	28
Museum	21
International organization	16
Total	4908

Source: Own elaboration

- a) Professional societies/Learned societies: National or disciplinary scientific associations.
- b) University: Faculties or institutes publishing journals.
- c) Others: Not identified within any specific category; Entities not classifiable under other categories; often includes national publishing companies or private editorial funds .
- d) Foundation/Mega-journals: Primarily includes publishers such as MDPI and Frontiers, as well as mega-journals like PLOS ONE.
- e) Commercial publisher: Includes the "Big Five" and other large publishers such as Kluwer or Cambridge University Press.
- f) Centre/Centro: Research centers.
- g) University press/Editorial Universitaria: University-based publishing houses.
- h) Governmental: Government editorial funds.
- i) Colegio/College/School: Institutions of higher education.
- j) Journal: Scientific journals managing their own editorial processes.
- k) Museum: Editorial houses funded by museums.
- l) International organization: publishing institutions funded by international organizations.

To compile Argentina's scientific output and classify the publishers we created a multisource database (Wos, Scopus, Lens, DOAJ, Ulrichweb, Google Scholar, Unpaywall). This was built through an automated ETL (extraction, transformation and load) process. It includes Boolean operators to identify the type of open access, the specific information of the journal, and the publisher associated with each document. The data from the integrated database was normalized to guarantee the uniqueness and correct assignment of each article and affiliations. Data collection was carried out in June 2021, with limited updates to certain fields, such as the access route provided by the OpenAlex methodology. We restricted our analysis to records with a DOI, resulting in a total of 139,412 publications. The use of WoS and Scopus retrieves all the information about commercial journals, Unpaywall, GS, and Lens lets us retrieve information about non-indexed journals in WoS or Scopus, mainly journals published in Spanish. Doaj and Ulrich have enriched information about the sources, as is the case for OpenAlex which has been used for the general control. All the sources finally converged into unique records.

Table 2. Sources and number of records collected per database.

Database	Article records 2013-2020	Access type
Web of Science	96,081	Subscription
Scopus	88,727	Subscription
Unpaywall	130,515	Public
Google Scholar	96,420	Public
Lens	90,690	Public
Editorials identified with the categories of DOAJ	17,564	Public
Articles with information for the publishers in Ulrich	114,872	Public
Total unique articles with DOI	139,412	
Total articles with DOI and access information in OpenAlex	123,147	
Total unique articles with DOI and publisher information in Ulrich	114,872	
Total unique articles affiliated with CONICET	65,877	

Source: WoS, Scopus, Unpaywall, Google Scholar, Lens, DOAJ, UlrichWeb, OpenAlex, CONICET database.

This research followed a two-stage methodological approach. In the first stage, we conducted a component network analysis of the output of Argentina (2013-2020) according to the type of publisher, access routes and costs. This stage allows for the characterization of the circulation models offered by different publishers to researchers. The second stage considers the researchers' degrees of dependence on the commercial publishing circuit, by discipline, based on the number of articles published in the different routes, and with various types of associated costs. This method allows us to build a map of journals and reclassify the publishers according to their business models and researchers' selection to understand the constraints produced by commercial open access. The multisource perspective of the database of articles is combined with a "bottom up" design for the researchers subset, based on the publications of a concrete scientific community and not extracting a population of authors from biased global sources

We mapped the publishers of the scientific output of Argentina revealing a highly diversified publishing landscape. This includes numerous publishing conglomerates and commercial alliances, along with the significant presence of non-commercial publishers. The relationships were analyzed in terms of article volume, access routes, and APC payments, classifying the publishers according to shared components. Let us consider the universe of articles produced by Argentine authors during the 2013-2020 period.

The analyses of the behavior of publishers and their strategic alliances were conducted using the 114,872 articles with publisher information enriched from Ulrichweb and access information enriched by OpenAlex. The analysis of the disciplinary patterns was performed based on the total articles with at least one CONICET-affiliated author (See Table 2). For this phase, we focused on Argentina's most internationalized research community, CONICET. To identify CONICET researchers we cross-referenced our database with a complementary national source built for a previous study (Beigel, Almeida et al 2023). The following indicators were observed: distribution of articles by publisher type; APC payments aggregated by publisher types; Access routes and Number of articles by disciplinary area. This methodology builds on Prosopography inspired in the bourdieusian field approach (Duval, 2020). It is a kind of "collective biography" that has the advantage of observing a situated scholarly community based on the study of relational features of the individuals belonging to the same space, collecting biographical information in addition to its scholarly output (Digiampietri, Gallardo, Baranger & Beigel, 2024).

3. Results

The scientific output analyzed in this paper reveals the existence of different publishing circuits that cross through Argentina's scientific field. It also sheds light on new alliances among publishers, and explains the resilience of non-commercial, diamond open-access journals published solely by public universities. Indeed, the primary driver behind the development of "high-impact" journals is indexation and the symbolic prestige acquired by the publishers -and perceived as such by the researchers- that operates through the accumulative best performance in journal rankings. However, digitalization and the open access movement have provided alternative circuits and different routes for publishing even within the same journal.

We identified four indicators that can distinguish a significant attachment or, in contrast, grades of autonomy from the path dependency to the dominant value regime established by the "high impact" journals: (1) Volume of articles published, (2) the type of Publisher or publisher alliance; (3) the relationship between APC costs and citation impact; and (4) Access routes of the journals. The combination of these factors shapes and diversifies publishing circuits according to the area of expertise. The research community under study in this paper is featured by an institutional culture addressed to international recognition and leadership that has a long tradition in Argentina's CONICET (Beigel, 2017). Tenure and promotion are organized by the "career-best publications", typically in Q1 journals, in English, with first authorships highly scored. This homogenizes a career path towards the "mainstream" publishing circuit and international journals. But interestingly, it does not exclude other researcher profiles more aligned with national or regional scholarly publishing styles. In the social sciences and humanities (SSH), institutional regulations provide specific criteria for evaluating the journals, equating the global indexations such as Scopus or Wos with regional indexations such as Scielo or Latindex.

(1) and (2) Volume of articles published and the morphology of the publishers.

We firstly analyzed the total of 114,872 articles from the database and the 4,908 publishers. In Figure 1, the editorial alliances and the distribution of the different publishing institutions can be observed.

Figure 1. Relationships between publishers through the journals they oversee, featuring publications by Argentine authors from 2013 to 2020

Total articles: 114,872. Number of publishers (n): 4,908. Color legends: Yellow: Commercial publishers, 248; Blue: University publishers, 1,533; Green: Professional societies/learned societies, 1,762; Red: Mega-journals/institutes, 287. Each line represents one or several shared journals. The size of the dots represents the number of articles attributed to each publisher. Note: Figure created with Pajek (Batagelj & Mrvar, 1998).

In Figure 1 the most prominent alliances can be observed at the top left, where commercial publishers dominate with a significant volume of publications (this cluster is shown in more detail in Figure 3). The commercial publishers dominate with a publication volume of 66,807 articles, representing 58.1% of the total articles published by Argentina (114,872). Collaboration between different publishers report 14,845 articles (12.9% of the total) being the most frequent alliances those of commercial publishers with others (855, 0.7% of the total), commercial publishers and megajournals/foundations (674, 0.5% of the total), professional societies with others (577, 0.5% of the total), and universities with university presses (1,009, 0.8% of the total).

When considering these publisher alliances in aggregate, they can be interpreted as strategies for market expansion and for increasing impact. Big commercial publishers stand out as the active agents in these alliances, interacting with all other 11 types of publishers. Notably, the relationships between commercial publishers and professional societies/learned societies (which will be further explored through cluster analyses) stand out. It is also interesting to observe that the alliances between university journals and university presses may reflect a process of merging the traditional division of labor of in Latin American journals (traditionally published by portals) while university presses used to publish only books.

(3) The relationship between APC costs and citation

Regarding the total APC cost for Argentina, the data shows concentration in 3 agents: commercial publishers, alliances between professional societies/learned societies and commercial publishers/megajournals with research institutes. It also shows that APC costs in journals owned by professional societies/learned societies are half price compared to the higher costs when publishing in alliances with commercial publishers. Universities generally do not charge APCs. Megajournals/Foundation compete with commercial publishers through an aggressive open access strategy, as the average APC paid per article is USD 345 for commercial publishers and USD 1,105 for Megajournals, whose APC-based model was consolidated over a decade ago.

Figure 2. Relationship between APC costs and citations for the total articles from Argentina 2013-2020 (n= 114,872)

As shown in Figure 2, most citations are concentrated in journals published by major commercial publishers. Meanwhile, megajournals have a higher average APC payment but much lower citation impact. In contrast, it is notable that professional societies/learned societies journals maintain lower APC costs and show a higher citation impact. On the other hand, university journals/university presses rarely charge APC, and when they do, the amounts are very low, but their citation impact is generally limited.

4) Access routes

The relationship between APC costs and citations is relevant not only for understanding the open access options available to the authors, but also to focus attention on hybrid model journals, which, in our view, have become central in the recent transformations of scholarly publishing. We used two sources of information available for classifying the access routes of the journals: a) OpenAlex⁵, which harvests the access route of each article based on several available options on the web and b) the classification used by Butler et al. (2022a)⁶ based on the control of the information offered by the journal. By combining these two datasets and cross-checking them, we were able to identify journals with a hybrid model more accurately. We observed that articles that paid to publish in hybrid journals were identified in OpenAlex frequently as diamond, but also as gold or green (18,145). Disregarding records without access information, the rest (15,439) were informed as without payment of APC, and remaining in closed format. Access routes discovered by OpenAlex, contrasted with declared routes from Butler et al, show that the hybrid journals represent a highly valued venue with scarce transparency that may be fostering a regression in open access. The dataset by Butler et al. (2022a) only considered the six largest commercial publishers (Elsevier, MDPI, Frontiers, PLOS, Springer-Nature, and Wiley), which is why we only analyzed a total 39,114 registered as hybrid out of the 123,147 total records included in our study.

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4. Discussion: circuits of recognition related to the path dependency from commercial publishers

The path dependency from high-impact journals established by the evaluation policies directly influence the variety of publishing circuits existing in a country like Argentina. Here, we use the concept of circuit as a space for the communication of research with different performances according with the recognition that the journals included can provide for career-building. This performance is based on two factors: (a) the value given by academic evaluation to journals indexed in certain services (such as the encouragement of indexing in WoS-Scopus, the acceptance/rejection of regional services or the de-valuation of local journals, for example), and (b) the publication routes according to different fields of knowledge, as further explored in the following section. These publishing circuits are intervened by the associative structures of publishers which directly impact editorial processes and the cost of their journals.

In what follows, the identification of publishing circuits is achieved by weighting dependency in terms of the type of publisher, the access and APC amount of the journal. This procedure generates a final scale with the total weight of these elements that allows us to observe the levels of dependency across publication routes, and identify the types of alliances that shape the different publishing circuits. In Table 3 the categories are not only publishers, but alliances between publishers when it is the case for a given group of articles. That is why commercial publishers appear many times, in alliance with diverse organizations.

Table 3. Weighting of path dependency according to publishers, access routes and APC costs (n= 114,782)

Publisher or publisher alliances	Articles (n)	APC (USD)	APC amount	Route 1	Route 2	Total weight
Commercial publishers	51,962	17,942,030	5	2	4	11
University	18,091	239,151	2	1	0	3
Professional societies/learned societies	12,744	1,845,114	3	2	0	5
Commercial publishers and Professional societies/learned societies	12,568	3,426,007	3	4	2	9
Others	5,762	1,116,961	3	3	4	10
Foundation/Megajournal	4,597	5,083,511	4	4	1	9
University press service	1,434	18,772	1	1	0	2
Governmental	1,041	4,135	1	1	0	2
University/University press service	1,009	2,861	1	1	0	2
Commercial publishers and Others	855	180,591	2	4	2	8
Centre/Centro	675	26,256	1	1	0	2

Commercial publishers and Foundations/ Megajournals/Institutes	674	18,204	2	2	4	8
Professional societies/learned societies and Others	577	93,058	1	3	4	8
Colegio/College/Escuela	414	29,384	1	1	4	6
Commercial publishers and Universities	295	20,416	1	4	2	7
Museum	250		1	1	0	2
International organization	207	104,274	2	1	2	5
Professional societies/learned societies and Foundations/Megajournals/Institutes	185		1	4	0	5
Commercial publishers and Governmental institutions	155		1	2	4	7
University and Others	145	4,902	1	1	0	2
Commercial publishers and Centre-Centro	136		1	4	4	9
Centre-Centro and Governmental institution	128		1	1	0	2
Professional societies/Learned societies and University press services	122	1,670	1	2	1	4

Source: Own elaboration.

References: The weight of APC is organized in 5: a) greater than 10,000,000 = 5; b) between 5,000,000 and 9,999,999 = 4; c) between 1,000,000 and 4,999,999 = 3; d) between 100,000 and 999,999 = 2; and e) less than 100,000 or 0 = 1.

Route 1 corresponds to the most frequent access route for all articles published by journals managed by the publisher or alliance according to OpenAlex data, and route 2 is the second most frequent. The weight is attributed by authors, and the ponderation is derived from the calculation on the frequencies that allow for calculating the Mode. Route weighting: hybrid = 5 (read & publish), gold = 4 (author pays), closed = 4 (reader pays), bronze = 3 (possible reader costs), green = 2 (possible author costs), diamond = 1 (costs covered by publisher).

Table 3 shows a gradient of dependency levels, ranging from high barriers (resulting from highest APC and the hybrid model that includes the high-impact journals) to diamond open-access circuits that are free of paywalls. The forms of associativity that impose greater barriers are concentrated on the commercial side, while the diamond journals are predominantly found in university-based publishing. If we analyze the total weighting for publisher's relationships into quartiles, the first and second quartiles include commercial publishers and their alliances with professional societies/learned societies, foundation/megajournals/institutes, centers, and other presumably smaller commercial publishers. These two quartiles represent a high dependency on the monetization of knowledge circulation. The other two quartiles are composed of universities, centers, institutes, and other academic or governmental organizations. In general terms, these publishing circuits are featured by non-monetized journals.

Mapping these publisher alliances highlight clear patterns of interaction, concentration, but also community-led journals. We identify 280 groups, each representing at least one partnership among 1,967 publishers. In contrast, 2,991 publishers operate independently, mostly university journals (represented in blue in Figure 1). Each group reflects a specific associative framework in which a set of journals is published. These groups have a particular characteristic: their structure resembles a star. This implies that there is one publisher that defines the association frameworks with a set of publishers of different types that orbit around it. This allows for the accumulation of academic value, such as between a commercial publisher and a large or small set of professional societies/learned societies, or between a university press service and different university departments of a university. These grouping strategies respond to different philosophies in managing editorial processes and in financing publication and, consequently, in knowledge circulation.

Based on these structural patterns observed we organize six groups according with the degrees of commodification: 1) Big commercial clustering; 2) Commercial publisher/megajournal/institute and learned societies; 3) Commercial publishers and national academies (small alliances); 4) Governmental publishing services; 5) Academic alliances; and 6)

Go-alone model (university journals operating independently, without association with any type of publisher).

1. Big commercial clustering: Groups dominated by large commercial companies in association with various types of publishers. Due to the predominance of commercial agents, these clusters generate significant dependency according to the weighting allocation table. There is only one group out of the 280 belonging to this category. Within this structure, professional societies and learned societies have adopted a commercial strategy to gain profits from their knowledge circulation channels in perfect alliance with commercial publishers. These societies manage to expand their publication offerings by delegating these functions to commercial publishers. These societies manage to expand their publication offerings by delegating these functions to commercial publishers.

Figure 3. Big commercial clustering.

Source: Own creation using Pajek software (Batagelj & Mrvar, 1998).

The yellow points represent commercial publishers, the green points represent professional societies and learned societies, the red points indicate foundation-megajournals-institute, and the blue points represent university and university press services. The relationships represent jointly published journals. A significant share of these publications is concentrated within this group, as can be seen in Figure 1.

2. Commercial publisher/megajournal/institute and professional societies/learned societies: Most of the relationships in the 30 groups classified under this type occurred between commercial publishers and scientific societies. These relationships have an average weighting of 9 and a standard deviation of approximately 2, which allows assigning the highest weighting in the table in terms of dependence. Commercial publishers expand their operations by establishing commercial relationships with national professional societies and learned societies. This allows commercial publishers to broaden their market by taking over the editorial function in professional societies and learned societies and increasing revenue through their journals.

Table 4. Example of network of alliances between commercial services and learned societies

Springer Japan KK with learned societies and universities:

Nippon Dobutsu Kodo Gakkai / Japan Ethological Society
United Nations University
Korean Society for Plant Biotechnology
Japanese Society for Artificial Organs
Han-guk Pyogmul Jawon Bunhwan Hakae / Korea Society of Waste Management
Ichthyological Society of Japan / Nihon Gyorui Gakkai
Nihon Shukushuku Gakkai / Japanese Society of Gastroenterology
Nihon Kotsu Tansha Gakkai / Japan Society for Bone and Metabolism Research
Japanese Association of Anatomists / Nihon Kaibo Gakkai
Physiological Society of Japan
The Society for Environmental Economics and Policy Studies
Japan Monkey Centre / Nihon Monki Senta
Japanese Breast Cancer Society
Japanese Association for Thoracic Surgery
Nihon Shokushutsu Byori Gakkai / Physiopathological Society of Japan
Japanese Gastric Cancer Association
The International Society for Extremophiles
Japanese Society of Applied Entomology and Zoology / Nihon Oyo Dobutsu Konchu Gakkai
Nihon Rikigaku Gakkai / Japanese Society of Limnology
Japanese Society of Echocardiography
Japanese Association of Cardiovascular Intervention and Therapeutics
Japanese Association of Forensic Toxicology / Nihon Ho Chudoku Gakkai
Japanese Society of Hematology

Source: Own elaboration.

3. Small commercial publishers and national academies (small alliances). This includes relationships between commercial publishers and others, which report an average dependency weighting of 6.2, indicating a medium level of dependency. This group presents a more diverse landscape. The standard deviation is 3.3, which implies the existence of small alliances with commercial publishers, alliances between editorial services of different academic institutions, and other similar derived publishing strategies. In total, 121 groups fall into this category.

Table 5. Example of network of alliance between small commercial publishers and national academies

Brepols publishers with universities, and learned societies.

Association pour l'Antiquite Tardive
Universite Catholique de Louvain / Bureau de la Revue d'Histoire Ecclesiastique
Brepols Publishers
Classical Association of the Atlantic States
National Endowment for Democracy
American Studies Association
University of California
Societe d'Histoire Religieuse de la France

The Jhon Hopkins University Press with other universities and learned societies.

Classical Association of the Atlantic States
National Endowment for Democracy
American Studies Association
University of California
Societe d'Histoire Religieuse de la France
Melville Society
American Mathematical Society
Mariana and Sciences Publishers
The Johns Hopkins University Press
University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston
Association for Applied Psychophysiology
University of Warwick Mathematics Institute
North American Patristics Society
Society for the History of Technology

Source: Own elaboration..

These examples inform three major forms of grouping that show a significant process of co-optation by commercial companies, which is only possible with the consent of scientific associations. In addition to publishing, these commercial publishers offer services such as indexing, impact ranking enhancement, artificial intelligence tools, and other derivative services, all of which also contribute to rising APC costs, as well as the agreements or subscriptions paid by institutions. Given that a substantial portion of the publications analyzed in this study fall under these models, the growing tendency of the journals managed by large commercial publishers can be foreseen.

4. Governmental publishing services: This category includes editorial services managed by government institutions. Their dependency weighting is low, based on the types of

relationships observed. In total, there are 2 groups with a total weighting of 2, reflecting minimal dependence in terms of monetization.

5. Academic alliances: These groups are composed of university editorial services and academic institutions, scientific societies, or research centers, in some cases through their editorial services. In total, there are 94 groups, with an average weighting of 2.4 and a standard deviation of 3.4, a figure that does not exceed the last two quartiles, indicating low dependence on the monetization of knowledge.

Table 6. Example of academic alliances

Servicio de publicaciones de la Universidad Complutense de Madrid and faculties that edit journals within the university.

Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Departamento de Biblioteconomia y Documentacion * Facultad de Educacion
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Escuela de Relaciones Laborales
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Bellas Artes
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Departamento de Ciencias y Tecnicas Historiograficas
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Unidad de Investigacion sobre Cooperacion y Seguridad Internacional
Asociacion de Psicooncologia de Madrid
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Derecho
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Filosofia
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Ciencias Politicas y Sociologia
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Servicio de Publicaciones
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Ciencias Biologicas
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Instituto Universitario de Ciencias Ambientales
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Escuela Universitaria de Trabajo Social
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Escuela Universitaria de Biblioteconomia y Documentacion
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Filologia
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Ciencias Fisicas
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Ciencias de la Informacion
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Geografia e Historia
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Farmacia
Asociacion Espanola de Geografia
Universidad Complutense de Madrid * Facultad de Ciencias Sociales

Source: Own elaboration.

6. Go-alone: This category includes journals published independently by publishers that do not form alliances with any organizations. The landscape of this group is diverse but low in terms of the weighting on the dependence of monetization.

In summary, the discussion shows that 64.9% of the articles are subject to some type of commercial publishing model, regardless of the access routes, mostly associated with Elsevier, Springer-Nature, and Wiley. Additionally, a significant portion of the articles published by megajournals such as PLoS, MDPI, and Frontiers, which charge substantial APCs, can be aggregated to this pattern. An important number of scientific societies in alliance with commercial publishers also charge APCs. However, it is important to note that in the journals led by learned scientific societies, green and gold open access routes still predominate.

The volume of publications by commercial publishers, journals with high APC rates, and those that require subscription payments, constitutes the dominant circuit for scholarly communication in Argentina. Scientific societies that once published a journal independently and are now partnered with commercial publishers have strongly contributed to the consolidation of this model, while the 6 different types of groups warn that, despite the concentration evidenced by commercial

publishers, there is a diversification of the market observable in the various alliances. In this context, hybrid journals play a very important role in a non-hegemonic country like Argentina. This necessarily implies a structural limitation on access to research results, either due to the monetization of APC payments or the reduced visibility produced by publication in the closed mode of hybrid journals—a phenomenon that is gradually increasing.

Path dependency of the commercial circuit by discipline

It is now time to auscultate the effects of this path dependency regarding the commercial circuit considering the internationalized evaluative culture of CONICET. To examine the relationships between the dynamics of the publishing market the value regimes that are outlined by global standards by discipline, we selected 65,867 articles from our database linked to researchers affiliated with CONICET. In table 5 each article is categorized according with the self-declared disciplinary affiliation of the Argentine authors in our previous study (Digiampietri et al., 2025). The use of this classification is relevant to our study because it is built by the self-adscription of the discipline provided by each researcher, a procedure that we see as improving the disciplinary classification of the articles inferred by the journals. It is meant to observe the behavior of each research community in relation with the criteria that is established by the evaluation committees that are organized in this distribution in Argentina’s CONICET as showed in Table 5.

The CONICET has special regulations for the evaluation of the social sciences and humanities for tenure and promotion. It advises evaluation committees to value publications in WoS or Scopus as equivalent to those as Scielo or Latindex. It also discourages the use of the Impact Factor. Although some disciplines within SSH -such as Arqueology- exhibit a 'mainstream' pattern similar to the natural and exact sciences where the high-impact journals are more valued (Baranger & Beigel, 2024).

Table 4. Number of articles by disciplinary area -CONICET. N=65,687

Disciplinary Area	Total general
Biology	7,472
Medical Sciences	5,036
Chemical Sciences	4,471
Process Engineering	4,430
Earth, Water, and Atmospheric Sciences	4,321
Physics	4,307
Biochemistry and Molecular Biology	3,597
Agricultural Sciences	3,421
Materials Engineering and Technology	1,998
Veterinary	1,869
Civil, Electrical, Mechanical Engineering, and Related Engineering	1,463
Archaeology and Biological Anthropology	1,337
Technological and Social Development of Complex Projects	1,329
Mathematics	1,275

Psychology and Educational Sciences	1,241
Sociology, Social Communication, and Demography	1,140
Environment, Conservation, and Sustainability	949
History and Geography	869
Astronomy	865
Computer Science and Communications	707
Literature, Linguistics, and Semiotics	619
Philosophy	602
Economics, Management, and Administration	596
Law and Political Sciences	533
Anthropology	408
Habitat and Design	334

Source: CONICET database.

The articles published by the CONICET researchers were distributed across the different types of publisher alliances and strategies, and their dependency weighting was calculated according to Table 3. As a result, we can see in Table 5 that SSH disciplines such as Sociology, Communications, Demography, History, Geography, Law, Political Science, and Anthropology predominantly publish through universities. These publishing circuits have neither access nor publication barriers, but they also have less access to international citation services and therefore limited visibility. However, this diversity observed in terms of circulation is due to the fact that these journals lead to rewards in the academic career within CONICET for these disciplines. In contrast with the SSH, the rest of the evaluation committees predominantly value the commercial route for publication, rewarding the Q1 ranked journals and prominent author positions.

Table 5. Path dependency by discipline (evaluation committee) and type of publisher (n =65,687).

Path dependency	9	11	9	9	2	10	10	8	8	3	3
Publishers type	Com-Pub	Com-Pub	Foun-d	Foun-d	Go-vern	Otro-s	Otro-s	Pro-Soc	Pro-Soc	Uni-v	Uni-v
Environment, Conservation, and Sustainability	106	564	16	51	6	8	57	51	32	46	16
Anthropology	10	76	13	13	10	3	12	10	13	113	124
Archaeology and Biological Anthropology	169	525	6	35	7	2	99	103	20	239	142
Astronomy	398	442	2			316	18	10	2	3	4
Biology	1015	4353	99	380	64	60	437	452	458	127	108
Biochemistry and Molecular Biology	502	2087	25	230	10	15	204	223	426	20	8
Agricultural Sciences	529	2083	16	128	17	7	116	216	127	96	24
Earth, Water, and Atmospheric Sciences	464	2647	96	80	9	7	155	567	172	83	46
Medical Sciences	798	3195	34	279	13	24	341	145	367	32	18
Chemical Sciences	451	2544	26	55	3		102	688	622	18	18
Law and Political Sciences	15	113	14	13	8	3	11	7	11	156	151
Technological and Social Development of Complex Projects	178	841	51	43	9	1	83	57	50	22	42
Economics, Management, and Administration	32	295	9	4	4	1	34	13	18	79	89

Philosophy	31	159	1	4	13	2	36	14	25	154	93
Physics	217	2891	57	100		16	90	681	257	11	19
Habitat and Design	16	102	1	2	11	1	21	5	18	126	36
History and Geography	17	141	46	7	51	7	46	26	13	323	181
Informatics and Communications	58	467	71	9		1	15	20	34	16	6
Civil, Electrical, Mechanical Engineering, and Related Engineering	149	809	226	52	1	2	54	52	42	30	27
Process Engineering	803	2879	11	47	7	9	142	233	206	53	41
Materials Engineering and Technology	232	1303	18	21	2		54	107	160	22	71
Literature, Linguistics, and Semiotics	21	178		4	12	26	39	14	11	172	117
Mathematics	88	854	37	7	2	14	101	108	81	12	18
Psychology and Educational Sciences	60	379	14	24	6	3	56	34	73	339	212
Sociology, Social Communication, and Demography	37	251	16	9	32	1	42	30	31	403	264
Veterinary Medicine	315	1112	6	71	11	2	60	62	73	74	18
Total general	6711	31290	911	1668	308	531	242	3928	3342	276	189
							5			9	3

Source: Own elaboration⁷.

References: ComPub (Commercial Publisher), ProSoc (Professional societies- learned societies), Found (Foundation-Megajournal-Institute), Govern (Governmental), Univ (Universities).

5. Conclusions

Although the Argentine case demonstrates that certain disciplines still circulate within university publications, the majority of the researchers publish in journals led by commercial publishers. As we argued in a previous study (Beigel, 2021) this reveals a form of 'alienation' between the investment that governments make to expand technologies for sharing open research and the tendency of evaluation systems to legitimize publishing circuits based on the monetization of knowledge circulation. The anatomy presented in this paper based on the associativity between different types of publishers unfolds the existence of various commercial strategies with a shared goal: to gain legitimacy among authors and readers. The main alliances pointing in this direction are those between professional societies/learned societies and commercial publishers, research centers with foundations/megajournals, and national alliances with satellite commercial publishers (branches of a central matrix).

All these strategies increased monetization, but still represented credible journal rankings that were used by the evaluation committees at CONICET as main criteria for tenure and promotion, thus being the main route for prestige-building during the period analyzed in this paper. This explains the high degree of path dependency from commercial publishers observed in Table 3. It also sheds light to the low degrees of dependency observed in several SSH disciplines. The evaluation system at the CONICET went through relevant changes during COVID-19 and a major shift towards more qualitative evaluation occurred in 2023. The effects of these changes in the path dependency patterns observed in this paper will be possible to assess only in the next years comparing for example with the output of the period 2021-2028.

The progressive concentration of publishing volume in the commercial circuit creates an increasing conflict in terms of the market pressure over journals and authors. This may contribute to highlighting autonomous academic journals in the context of heteronomous evaluation regimes

⁷ Only the cases with the highest number of articles per discipline are highlighted. A limitation of this analysis is that only articles with DOI could be included, likely excluding a significant number of articles that circulate outside the commercial circuit.

that are globally under scrutiny. For this reason, it is crucial to consider the diversity of associative models to favor the diamond route, following the recommendations of the Global Summit on Diamond Access (Toluca 2023 and Cape Town 2024). Local or national alliances between small publishers, university journals, and other academic actors have achieved sustainable nonprofit open access, largely due to regional publishing platforms such as SciELO or Redalyc. These alliances seem to have positive effects on audience size and the increase of editorial capacities at less costs. This could be a way forward for hundreds of isolated university journals as a strategy to solve management issues and the problems that hinder visibility.

Our results reveal an initial trend of open access backwardness led by hybrid route journals that attract prestigious researchers that cannot/are not willing to pay APCs. These journals play a relevant role in establishing a segmentation of “excellence” within the mainstream circuit and therefore may need to be reconsidered in scientometric studies to better inform responsible research assessment. We believe that the extent of this trend is yet likely underestimated due to a lack of transparent information from the journals⁸. It becomes clear that the Plan S initiative failed to fully consider the negative side effects of commercial open access and the transformative agreements. The speed of the process did not allow the preparation of market regulations, which led to the escalation of publication prices and the growth of the hybrid model which can become an increasingly frequent pathway for the retreat of open access.

Behind the scenes of the current state of scholarly publishing, the alliances observed show that commercial publishers have an active role in accumulating symbolic capital by segmenting circuits of recognition to increase their profits. If this situation remains unaltered, the specialized audiences of the prestigious journals can become increasingly blurred. Editorial processes seem to be more and more standardized by commercial publishers, marginalizing academic editorship. Transitioning to a non-commercial and democratized model to counteract these trends within the so called “mainstream” circuit requires market regulations to establish fairer pricing structures. In contrast, for other publishing circuits that already develop in non-monetized environments the challenge is still anchored in gaining visibility.

Statements and Declarations

The authors declare no competing interests.

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⁸ We are currently enlarging this empirical observation in research in progress.

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